

THE SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL LESSONS OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF EDUCATIONAL SUBJECTS

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Annotation: the article covers regulatory legal acts-the concept of science, State Educational Standards, Curriculum, methodological recommendations, calendar-plans, technologies for teaching science, lesson developments, additional resources that reveal the goals and objectives of the discipline "upbringing". The curriculum and textbooks of the discipline "upbringing" emphasize the formation of skills such as patriotism, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsiveness, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, hard work. In particular, national traditions, life and ways of the Great Gods, works, the activities of contemporary heroes were widely used as an example in this. Advanced technology and methods of teaching, such as "Project-based teaching", "interest-based teaching", "Art-fest", "exemplifying", "teaching through examples", "situation analysis", which are popular worldwide today, have been used in teaching topics.

Keywords: upbringing, science, program, work, responsiveness, tolerance, law culture, innovation, ideology, Immunity, Project.

According to the data, in general secondary institutions, the subject of "upbringing" is taught 1 hour a week in grades 1-11, and 34 hours during the school year. A methodological manual was also developed for teachers, which included modern approaches to organizing classes in the subject of "upbringing". A manual entitled "technology for teaching the discipline" was prepared for publication. In order to create an information platform for educational and methodological support in the field of "education", the internet network www.tarbiyam.uz in the domain, a database was created that provides methodological assistance to the teacher, in which information and tasks for the subject are described. Regulatory legal documents revealing the goals and objectives of the discipline "education" for teachers-the concept of science, State Educational Standards, Curriculum, methodological recommendations, calendar-plans, technologies for teaching science, lesson developments, additional resources are being placed on this platform.

There are also special rucks for students and parents on the platform. Textbooks of " discipline " for grades 1-11 were created, and 21 videos on the topics in it were included in the textbooks with a QR code. To what extent is the emphasis in these textbooks on the use of modern pedagogical technologies that teach young people to think and serve to educate them as Patriots, faithful to our national values? The curriculum and textbooks of " upbringing " have a special emphasis on the formation of skills such as patriotism, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsiveness, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, hard work. In particular, national traditions, life and ways of the Great Gods, works, the activities of contemporary heroes were widely used as an example in this. Advanced technology and methods of teaching, such as "Project-based teaching", "interest-based teaching", "Art-fest", "exemplifying", "teaching through examples", "situation analysis", which are popular worldwide today, have been used in teaching topics.

The Cabinet of ministers adopted Resolution No. 422 of 06.07.2020 "on measures for the gradual implementation of the discipline "upbringing" in general secondary educational institutions". The unified discipline " upbringing "combines in grades 1-9 – the 2020-2021 academic year, and in grades 10-11- the subjects" etiquette", " sense of Homeland", " The idea of national independence and the basics of spirituality "and" the history of world religions " within the framework of the General hours allocated from the 2021-2022 academic year.

The document confirmed the following: - the composition of the group coordinating the creation of textbooks and educational and methodological complexes on the subject of "upbringing" for students of general secondary educational institutions; - the composition of the group of developers on the creation of textbooks and educational and methodological complexes on the subject of "upbringing" for students of general secondary educational institutions; - the concept of the subject "upbringing" for students of general secondary educational institutions. The following tasks were assigned to the Ministry of public education: - Development and approval of the state educational standard and curricula of general secondary education in the subject of " upbringing"; - Formation of orders for textbooks and educational and methodological complexes on a new subject intended for grades 1-9 of general secondary educational institutions for the 2020-2021 academic year by July 10, 2020 and for grades 10-11 for the 2021-2022 academic year by December 1; -

Conclusion of contracts with public and private publishing and printing organizations on the basis of exceptionally declared prices for printing textbooks and educational and methodological complexes intended for grades 1-9 by July 15, 2020 and for grades 10-11 by May 1, 2021; - Organization of printing textbooks and educational and methodological complexes on the subject of "upbringing" until the beginning of the new academic year and ensuring their delivery to the places; - From July 2020, until the beginning of the new academic year, on the basis of training programs and textbooks prepared for the subject of "upbringing", the organization of targeted training courses in the online form of "Education" in regional centers for teachers of Science with the specialties "Primary Education", "National idea and law", "history" and "Religious Studies; - experimental testing of textbooks and educational and methodological complexes prepared from a new subject during training courses.

The document defines: -The costs associated with the preparation and printing of textbooks and educational-methodological complexes on the subject of "upbringing" for publication, delivery, payment of fees to the developers are included in the total cost of textbooks and educational-methodological complexes; - The costs of purchasing and supplying textbooks and educational complexes on the subject of "upbringing" include students of the 1st grade of general secondary educational institutions, orphanages, specialized schools and boarding schools for children with disabilities in physical or mental development, children of families in need of social assistance and the publication of textbooks, multimedia applications and educational and methodological complexes for teachers on; - providing students with textbooks on the basis of rent-will be covered by the funds of the Republican Target Book Fund under the Ministry of public education. - The following tasks were assigned to the Ministry of higher and secondary special education, the Committee on Religious Affairs under the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministry of public education: - In 2020-2023, "primary education", "history" (by country and Region), "history teaching methodology", "philology and Language Teaching: Uzbek language", "Uzbek language and literature", "national idea, fundamentals of spirituality and law education", "pedagogy and psychology", "theology and Islamic Studies (Islamic history and sourcing)" of republican institutions of Higher Education. In 2020-2023, "primary education", "history" (by country and Region), "history teaching methodology", "philology and Language Teaching: Uzbek language", "Uzbek language and literature", "national idea, fundamentals of spirituality and law education", "pedagogy and psychology", "theology and Islamic Studies (Islamic

history and sourcing)" of republican institutions of Higher Education, Taking the necessary measures to give graduates of educational areas" psychology (sociopsychology of religion) "the right to teach the subject of" upbringing " in general secondary education schools and making appropriate.

The costs of procurement and delivery of textbooks and educational complexes on the subject of" upbringing " are covered by the Republican budget and funds of the Republican Target Book Fund under the Ministry of public education. The decision approved the concept of the subject "upbringing" for students of general secondary educational institutions. The cluster method of teaching the subject "upbringing" in primary education is an important factor in the elimination of pedagogical complexes. Pedagogical conflict is a set of conflicts that arise as a result of mutual misunderstanding in the process of education and upbringing. At the time of Anyini, pedagogical conflict is a fleeting conflict, conflict and discord, and there are options for their elimination. In this sense, in the process of teaching the subject of" upbringing " in a cluster method, there are opportunities to eliminate the following pedagogical conflicts: 1. Conflict in the student's self. In the self of an elementary student, conflicts sometimes arise that need to be resolved pedagogically, such as whims, disinterest in acquiring knowledge, prioritizing personal interests. "Discipline" eliminates conflicts in the student's self by implying identity.

The Signification of identity is achieved by introducing nationality, homeland and ancestry to the reader. For example, for this, awakening in the reader a feeling of love for the mother tongue gives the observed effect. In this respect, the following lines from the poem "mother tongue" by the poet Zulfiya Muminova can be memorized and explained the meaning: From Orkhun to Enasai - Haqan tilim, Sultan tilim say, Say a slice of Khos Hajibe-Eshan Eshan, There is no greater than you for me. Mother tongue-bozrukvar Shahim. You are there, so there is an Uzbek, My mother tongue is alampanohim. Such poems introduce the reader to their identity, namely nationality, homeland, and ancestral identity. As a result, the various conflicts that occur in the personality of the student naturally disappear. 2. The student's conflict with others. Since an elementary student is in physical, spiritual, and mental growth, it sometimes arises that he is in conflict with others. Such contradictions are manifested in such manifestations as rude attitude, disrespect, always striving to be the first.

The subject of "upbringing" has the opportunity to consistently solve such pedagogical complexes. In the experience of Uzbek upbringing, several ways are

described in this regard. For example, Abraham Qassar (9th century) says: "two things in this world of Man destroy the excitations in their hearts: 1) peer-to-peer conversation; 2) Service to mentors" So, in the process of teaching "upbringing", the conflicts that arise with others in an elementary student can be overcome by teaching them to talk and serve. According to him, an elementary school student who has a conflict in his heart with others is encouraged to talk more with his comrades (peers), and gradually gets used to being at the service of his teachers. In this respect, having the skills of conversation and service eliminates the feeling of students entering into conflict with others. 3) the student's conflict with the teacher.

In an elementary student, sometimes, under the influence of various factors, conflicts arise, such as not entering the word of his teacher, not doing what he says, lying to him. Such conflict is often caused by the negative word or opinion of peers or seniors about the mentor. For this reason, the teacher (teacher or mentor) must prematurely understand such conflicts, find reasons. Abu Ja'far Sumani (9th century), one of the noble thinkers, says: "Seni 1) friend-scares from sin; 2) Companion-shows your guilt; 3) Brother-elted to reality" In this respect, it is advisable for the teacher to accept the student as a friend, companion and brother in order to eliminate the conflicts that arise in the student towards him. Given the attention, the process of upbringing in the experience of our national pedagogy is based on timely elimination of pedagogical conflicts that occur in educators. For this, the Comprehensive activity of the teacher and the student is relied on.

Therefore, it is advisable to rely on the experiences of our national pedagogy when teaching "upbringing" to elementary students. After all, the system of overcoming pedagogical conflicts in the process of teaching the subject "upbringing" in primary education on the basis of the cluster method is perceived as follows (drawing 6). Such an approach allows primary school students to eliminate pedagogical conflicts in time when teaching the subject "upbringing". To do this, the teacher must always act as an aspiring innovator, accepting the educator as a companion and guiding him.

Teaching of educational subjects in the cluster method		
1-Stage	2-Stage	3-Stage
Determination of pedagogical competence.	Looking for a way to solve the problem.	Identification of participants in solving the problem.
Pedagogy to determine the manifestations of consistency.	Choosing a method for solving the problem.	Solving the problem in the short term
Observation and study.	Determination of the achievements of science.	Use of educational resources.
Effective elimination of pedagogical competence.		

The subject "upbringing" is new in the educational system of our country, the basics, methods and technologies of its teaching should be developed. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the skills of the teachers of this subject, prepare the teachers of the future primary class for it and carry out a large-scale scientific research work on problems. It is desirable that the experiences in this regard be coordinated. In the theory and practice of pedagogical conflicts, the following characteristics of students are considered: - changes in the mind of the reader; - what is happening in the moral understanding of the reader; - the environment that covers the reader; - attitude of the reader to others; - the student's interest in learning. Given the attention, these features are clearly noticeable in elementary school students.

Therefore, providing them with an educational and educational environment is an important issue. To do this, it is necessary to observe the atmosphere of upbringing being received in the family, study the atmosphere of school education and become aware of changes in the personality of the student. In the Prevention of pedagogical conflicts, the activity of teachers and coaches is primary. Therefore, in the process of upbringing, the status of teachers and coaches is a priority, according to which parents and the school team are involved in the educational process based on their conclusions. In conclusion, today, in the process of higher pedagogical education, it is advisable to prepare

teachers of the future primary class for the effective organization of educational classes, to develop theoretical knowledge and professional orientation in them. To do this, future specialists should be armed with methods of dividing, individual observation and solving their problems from scientific research on the effective organization of training classes.

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